

Nanoclay in Polymer/Fibre Composites

A.A. van Geenen; H.E.N. Bersee.
Delft University of Technology
Kluyverweg 1,
2629 HS Delft
The Netherlands
A.A.vanGeenen@TUDelft.nl

SUMMARY

The group Design and Production of Composite Structures, of the Delft University of Technology, investigates the possibilities for using thermoplastic composites containing polyamide-6, glass or carbon fibre, and nanoclay. The nanoclay is thought to reduce internal stresses, give a smoother surface and increase weather resistance. The results on dispersion and properties of the composites will be presented.

Keywords: Wind energy; thermoplastic; polymer/fibre composite; polyamide-6; anionic polymerisation; nanoclay

ABSTRACT

Nanoclay composites are well known. Because the aspect ratio of nanoclay is high (100-800), the insertion of small quantities (2 to 4 wt%) well dispersed nanoclay results in a higher modulus, especially above T_g of the polymer. This again leads to an increased Heat Distortion Temperature (HDT). For polyamide-6, the increase in HDT is about 50°C what makes it possible to use polyamide-6 under the hood and near the engine of a car.

In polymer films and at higher concentrations (>6 wt%), the nanoclay platelets will behave as a barrier for gases like water vapour. The nanoclay/polymer films can be used for food wrapping preventing the food for drying out, even when using thinner films.

The Delft University of Technology is part of a program for design and construction of windmills for energy to be placed in the North Sea. The DPCS group studies the possibilities for construction of windmill wings based on composites of thermoplastic polymers (especially polyamide-6) and glass or carbon fibre. In polymer/fibre composites, especially polyamide-6/glass or carbon fibre composites, well dispersed (exfoliated) nanoclay is thought to:

- reduce internal stresses of the composite material,
- provide a smoother surface and
- result in higher weather resistance

In practice, polyamide-6/nanoclay composites can be produced:

By hydrolytic polymerisation of mixtures of nanoclay and caprolactam to polyamide-6, this results in optimum exfoliation and dispersion of nanoclays.

Or: by compounding a mixture of on purpose treated nanoclays and polyamide-6 in an extruder, although dispersion and exfoliation by this method is less optimal.

For manufacturing of polyamide/glass fibre composites a practical choice is vacuum infusion. However, for vacuum infusion, the viscosity of molten polyamide is too high and therefore polyamide-6 cannot be infused in a stack of fibre mats. For obtaining the composites, we use in situ polymerisation: a mixture of caprolactam (monomer), activator and initiator is infused in a stack of fibre mats and after infusion; the monomer is converted in polyamide-6 by anionic polymerisation.

Exfoliation and dispersion of nanoclay during anionic polymerisation is not well known and is part of the research. Obtaining good exfoliation is not easy, one can do it right and do it wrong (see figures)

Polyamide-6 + 1 wt% Nanoclay.

Left side: bad exfoliation; right side: good exfoliation.

We will present our results of dispersion of nanoclays during in situ anionic polymerisation of caprolactam and mechanical data of the composites obtained.